

W-STEM: Building the future of Latin America: engaging women into STEM

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W-STEM Attraction campaigns

Tecnologico de Monterrey

Introduction

This document summarizes the activities carried out to inform and disseminate the experiences, opinions and perspectives of various figures involved in the development of STEM areas. It should be noted that in response to the conditions derived from the COVID-19 disease, efforts made as virtual events broadcast live and available on the project's official YouTube site are described. Details of those virtual events are then recorded.

Activities

Women and Girls in Science International Day

Date and time: February 11, 2020, 10:00 to 17:00

Objective: Promote women participation in STEM by having young women students in STEM areas sharing their testimonies about their “aha moment”. A step to break stereotypes and biases against women in STEM areas.

Participants: Angeles Dominguez (Coordinator), Itzel Hernández (Mexico), Josefina Muñoz (Mexico), Esmeralda Muñoz, Pablo Barniol, Genaro Zavala, Blanca Ruiz & Santa Tejeda

Target audience: high school students, parents, and wider audience.

Women in Science Day

Date and time: March 10, 2020;

Coordinator: Angeles Dominguez (Mexico) and Itzel Hernandez (Mexico).

Format: in-person

Place: Garden of races (near the Obelisk)

Screen: women in STEM within the Tec (profile: research.tec.mx)

Resources: Mural type roll to put a mark, signature, women's day message

Catering: Self-contained fruit (small apples, tangerines and bananas)

Round Table Girls in ICT

Date and time: April 23, 2020, 16:30 – 18:00 CEST 9:30 – 11:00 COT

Speaker: Adriana Buelvas (UTB Colombia), Ana Laura Monge (University of Costa Rica), Annye Braca (Technological University Dublin), Bertha Brenes (ITCR Costa Rica), Daniela Vizcarra (UdG Mexico), Jhenifer Guagala (UTN Ecuador), Karla Perales (Tec de Monterrey Mexico), Karla Rodríguez (UTPJ Ecuador), Kristell Urueta (UniNorte Colombia), Luisa Barrera (Politecnico di Torino Italy) and Marta Cortés (University of Oulu Finland).

Coordinator: Angeles Dominguez (Mexico), Alicia García (Spain) and Itzel Hernandez (Mexico).

Format: Video, live broadcast on Facebook and YouTube. Available at <https://youtu.be/v1135Aa8pSU>

Target audience: High school students interested in STEM areas and undergraduate students in STEM areas.

Objective of the activity: On the occasion of the Women in ICT Day, the opportunity was proposed for different international students to share their experiences as students of information technologies.

Roundtable Women in Mathematics

Date and time: May 12, 2020, 16:30 – 18:00 CEST 9:30 – 11:00 COT

Speaker: Ana Laura Montenegro (University of Costa Rica), Angie Vicente (UTPJ Ecuador), Arcelia Hernández (UdG Mexico), Alejandra González (Tec de Monterrey Mexico), Bárbara Núñez (PUCV Chile), Beatriz Barbero (University of Salamanca Spain), Claudia Álvarez (USM Chile), Giada Morat (Politecnico di Torino Italy), Gisel Mattar (Uni Norte Colombia), Lilibeth de Horta (UTB Colombia), Sandra Narváz (UTN Ecuador), Silvia Calderón (Universidad Oulu Finland) and Verónica Vargas (UdG Mexico).

Coordinator: Angeles Dominguez (Mexico), Alicia García (Spain) and Itzel Hernández (Mexico).

Format: Video, live broadcast on Facebook and YouTube. Available at <https://youtu.be/UeKr3rnm5PE>

Target audience: High school students interested in STEM areas and undergraduate students in STEM areas.

Objective of the activity: On the occasion of Women in Mathematics Day, a moment of reflection and discussion was opened on the link between mathematics in STEM areas and the importance of the participation of women in the development, study, and education of mathematics. math.

And so, I ended up dedicating myself to asteroids

Date and time: June 30, 2020, 17:00 – 18:30 CEST 10:00 – 11:30 COT

Speaker: Dr. Guadalupe Cordero (Institute of Geophysics, UNAM, Mexico), Dr. Rodolfo Barniol (Physics and Astronomy, California State University, USA), Dr. Santiago Torres (Leiden Observatory, The Netherlands), Phys. Yaleidys Paola Hernandez (UTB, Colombia).

Coordinator: Angeles Dominguez (Mexico), Esmeralda Campos (Mexico), Josefina Muñoz (Mexico) and Itzel Hernández (Mexico).

Format: Video, live broadcast on Facebook and YouTube. Available at <https://youtu.be/rXk0rAWBkLY>

Target audience: High school students interested in STEM areas and undergraduate students in STEM areas.

Objective of the activity: On the occasion of Asteroid Day we invite diverse experts in the scientific study of asteroids. Astronomy, biology, and many more STEM areas converge to help us better understand these celestial objects.

Social Networks in favor of STEM women, panel discussion

Date and time: December 09, 2020, 17:00 – 18:30 CEST 10:00 – 11:30 COT

Speaker: Cinthia Reyes (Mexico), Nataly Pozo (Ecuador) and Carolina Rodríguez (Mexico).

Coordinator: Angeles Dominguez (Mexico), Esmeralda Campos (Mexico) and Itzel Hernández (Mexico).

Format: Video, live broadcast on Facebook and YouTube. Available at <https://youtu.be/QKdNfKju6B8>

Target audience: High school students interested in STEM areas and undergraduate students in STEM areas.

Objective of the activity: We invite three STEM women who have ventured into the use of social networks for the dissemination and socialization of their passion for science and technology.

Redes Sociales
en pro de la mujer **STEM**

Carolina Rodríguez
Panelista

9 de diciembre
10:00 AM (MEX)

[f @lamujercohete](#)
[@lamujercohete](#)
 La Mujer Cohete

[f @wstemproject](#)

Redes Sociales
en pro de la mujer **STEM**

Nataly Pozo
Panelista

9 de diciembre
10:00 AM (MEX)

[@quieroser_ingeniera](#)
[@quieroseringeniera](#)
 @quieroseringeniera

[f @wstemproject](#)

Redes Sociales
en pro de la mujer **STEM**

Cinthia Reyes
Panelista

9 de diciembre
10:00 AM (MEX)

[@cinthiareyes](#)
[@elauladeCinthiaReyes](#)
[@ProfCinReyes](#)
 @ProfaCinthiaReyes
 www.cinthiareyes.com

[f @wstemproject](#)

International Day of the Girl and Women in Science, social media

Date: February 11, 2021 on the International Day of the Girl and Women in Science.

Speaker: Itzel Hernández Armenta

Objective: Attraction campaign to a broader audience, parents and students

Las mujeres en la ciencia
11 de febrero
Día internacional de la niña y la mujer en la ciencia

Wstem

Itzel Hernández Armenta
Doctorado en Innovación Educativa
armenta.itz@gmail.com

Día internacional de la niña y la mujer en la ciencia

- La igualdad entre hombres y mujeres es una prioridad global de la UNESCO, y el apoyo a las jóvenes, su educación y su plena capacidad para hacer oír sus ideas son los motores del desarrollo y la paz.
- La ciencia y la igualdad de género son fundamentales para el **desarrollo sostenible**. Aún así, las mujeres siguen encontrando obstáculos en el campo de la ciencia: **menos del 30% de investigadores científicos en el mundo son mujeres**.

Fuente: <https://es.unesco.org/commemorations/womenandgirlscienceday>

¿Qué es W-STEM project? Objetivo principal

- Building the future of Latin America: engaging women into STEM
- Mejorar las estrategias y mecanismos de atracción, acceso, acompañamiento y retención de las mujeres latinoamericanas en programas universitarios en áreas de ciencias, tecnología, ingeniería y matemáticas (STEM por sus siglas en inglés).

Queremos saber tus

- Experiencias y vivencias como estudiante universitaria STEM
- Inquietudes e ideas de mejora para tu experiencia
- Trayectoria desde que inició tu interés por tu carrera
- Que tu deseas un ejemplo para otras niñas y mujeres, promoviendo el empoderamiento a través de una **red de mentoras**
- ¡Contáctame!** (armenta.itz@gmail.com, WA 8111937814)

